

in IR26 was low. In plots planted to IR26, infection started at the border.

Low RTV infection in IR26 can be explained by the inability of RTBV-infected plants to serve as virus sources for spread of RTV infection and to the cultivar's resistance to RTSV. □

Resistance of rice varieties to rice tungro virus (RTV) and its green leafhopper (GLH) vector in Tamil Nadu, India

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We screened 12 commonly grown rice varieties against RTV and GLH *Nephotettix virescens* Distant in the greenhouse.

Seedlings (15 d old, 20/variety) were inoculated with RTV by releasing three viruliferous vectors on each test plant for a 24-h inoculation feeding. Inoculated plants were kept in an insect-proof cage for symptom expression. Infected seedlings were counted and infection severity graded 25 d after inoculation.

The same varieties were screened against GLH. Pregerminated seeds

Reaction^a of rice varieties to RTV and green leafhopper. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Rice tungro virus				Green leafhopper	
	Severity rating	Infected plants (%)	Scale based on percentage of infected phnts ^b	Reaction	Scale ^b	Reaction
PTB18	1	0	0	R	1	HR
IET6262	1	0	0	R	1	HR
TNAU13613	5	30	3	I	5	MR
IR26	7	40	5	I	5	MR
IR28	7	40	5	I	3	R
IR29	5	40	5	I	3	R
IR30	3	30	3	I	3	R
IR36	3	20	3	I	5	MR
IR50	1	0	0	R	5	MR
IR52	5	20	3	I	3	R
IR54	3	10	1	R	3	R
TN1	9	90	9	S	9	HS

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

were sown 3 cm apart in 20-cm rows in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden flats with 7-cm-deep soil. One week after sowing, the seedlings were thinned to 15/row and the flats transferred to 60- × 45- × 15-cm galvanized iron trays filled 10 cm deep with water. The trays were covered with an insect-proof cage.

Seedlings were infested with second- and third-instar nymphs of *N. virescens*. Plants containing nymphs were gently tapped over the seedlings so that 4-5 nymphs were released per seedling. Damage was rated 6 d after

infestation, when susceptible check TN1 seedlings were severely damaged.

PTB18, IET6262, and IR50 did not show symptoms of RTV infection (see table). IR54 was resistant to infection, with a severity value of 3. This is the first report of IET6262 showing RTV resistance under artificial inoculation. Other varieties showed moderate resistance.

PTB18 and IET6262 were highly resistant to GLH. IR26, IR36, IR50, and TNAU13613 showed moderate resistance. □

Insect resistance

Field evaluation of rice cultivars in India for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) causes serious damage to rice during rabi season (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr) in Kuttanad area of Kerala State. Outbreaks have been reported since 1973. In 1986-87, rice crops were hopperburned.

We evaluated 42 rice accessions from the All India Coordinated Rice

Accessions rated as highly resistant, resistant, and moderately resistant to BPH. Kerala, India, 1986-87.

Designation	Cross combination	BPH damage score ^a (0-9)			Damage rating ^b
		1986 kharif	1987 rabi	Mean	
RP1579-52-47	Phalguna/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP1579-28-54	Phalguna/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP2068-18-3-1	IET5656/Velluthacheera	1	1	1	HR
IRP2068-18-4-5	IET5656/Velluthacheera	1	1	1	HR
RP1579-1585-28-205	Phalguna/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP2547-1621-37-217	ARC5723/ARC6650//RP1579-38	1	1	1	HR
RP1976-18-6-4-2	IET5656/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP1960-1569-24-224	IET5656/IET5688	1	1	1	HR
KAU153-1	IR1561/PTB33	3	1	2	R
RP2068-32-6-1	IET5656/Velluthacheera	5	5	5	MR
RP2084-2-3-1	Phalguna/NLR96 74	5	3	4	MR
RP2084-74-5-2	Phalguna/NLR96 74	6	3	4.5	MR
CR400-21-1-1	IR20/CR95-112-8	5	3	4	MR
Sonasali		5	5	5	MR
Phalguna		7	3	5	MR

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

Improvement Project under heavy field incidence during 1986 kharif and 1987 rabi. Each accession was planted in 10-m² plots with a spacing of 20 × 15 cm, with two replications. Accessions were scored at panicle initiation (PI), when infestation was more than 200 insects/hill.

Eight accessions were found to be highly resistant (score 1) (see table). One was resistant (score 2) and six were moderately resistant (score 3-5). Twelve entries were moderately susceptible (score 5-7) and 15 were highly susceptible (score 7-9).

Almost all the highly resistant entries were derived from crosses involving ARC6650 or Velluthacheera. Resistant entry KAU153-1 was derived from IR1561/PTB33. □

Reaction of differential rice varieties to Manipur biotype of gall midge (GM)

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Seven GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason biotypes have been identified, one each in China, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Thailand, and three in India (Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, and Ranchi [Bihar]).

We evaluated six differentials (four donors and two derivatives from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad) against the GM population of Iroisemba, Manipur, in 1988 wet season. Thirty-day-old seedlings were planted in 3-m rows per variety at 15-

× 15-cm spacing. GM incidence was recorded at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT).

Potential donors Eswarakora and Banglei showed low damage; Leuang 152 and Velluthacheera showed higher. Resistant derivative W1263 showed no

damage; Phalguna was susceptible to the local GM population (see table).

These reactions of proven donors and derivatives show that the Manipur GM biotype conforms to the Ranchi GM biotype. □

Reaction of donors and derivatives to GM. Iroisemba, Manipur, India, 1988.

Variety	Donor, derivative	GM incidence (%)			
		30 DT		50 DT	
		Infested hills	Silvershoots	Infested hills	Silvershoots
Eswarakora	Donor	5	1	5	1
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	0	0	0	0
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	25	10	75	23
Leuang 152	Donor	15	4	35	10
Velluthacheera	Donor	0	0	50	12
Banglei	Donor	0	0	0	0
TN1	Susceptible check	30	11	75	29

Resistance of wild rices to insect pests

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We evaluated 185 wild rice accessions--16 species, 4 natural hybrids, and an unknown *Oryza* sp.—against *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix virescens*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, *Marasmia patnalis*, *Rivula atimeta*, *Hydrellia philippina*, and *Nymphula depunctalis*.

Reactions to planthoppers and leafhoppers were tested using the standard seedbox screening test. Reactions against foliage feeders were tested in the greenhouse. Resistance to *S. incertulas* and *N. depunctalis* was

Table 1. Resistance of wild rices to selected species of insect pests. IIRI, 1988.

Insect	Accessions tested (no.)	Resistant	
		no.	%
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 1	185	87	47
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 2	185	66	36
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 3	185	78	42
<i>N. virescens</i>	184	68	37
<i>S. furcifera</i>	185	83	45
<i>S. incertulas</i>	177	41	23
<i>C. medinalis</i>	176	0	0
<i>M. patnalis</i>	176	0	0
<i>R. atimeta</i>	176	0	0
<i>H. philippina</i>	172	13	8
<i>N. depunctalis</i>	172	0	0

evaluated in plants grown in concrete beds. Resistance to *H. philippina* was tested under natural infestation in the field. Plant damage was rated on a 0-9 scale.

Nearly 50% of the accessions were

Table 2. Species of wild rices with multiple resistance to *N. lugens*, *S. furcifera*, *N. virescens*, *S. incertulas*, and *H. philippina*. IIRI, 1988.

Species	IIRI Acc. no.	Origin
<i>O. alta</i>	100111	Surinam
<i>O. australiensis</i>	105165	Australia
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	105159	Uganda
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	105163	Uganda
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	105144	Brazil
<i>O. latifolia</i>	105142	Costa Rica
<i>O. minuta</i>	105126	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100176	Unknown
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105079	India
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105088	Malaysia
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105119	Philippines
<i>O. punctata</i>	100886	Unknown
<i>O. punctata</i>	105158	Uganda

resistant to *S. furcifera* and *N. lugens* biotypes 1 and 3, more than 35% to biotype 2 and *N. virescens*, 23% to *S. incertulas*, and 8% to *H. philippina* (Table 1). No accession was resistant